

Conference Abstract

Transforming inland water monitoring: integrating remote sensing and next-generation in situ technologies

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Abstract

Biodiversity loss, pollution, and the impacts of climate change have reached critical levels, creating the need for transformative changes in society and human behavior to reverse these trends and restore nature to a central place in people's lives. Effective environmental monitoring is essential to this effort, with a particular focus on aquatic environments - especially inland waters - due to their profound connections to society, human health, and climate systems.

In recent decades, satellite remote sensing has emerged as a powerful tool for monitoring water quality in inland water systems, driven by advances in orbital sensor technology. Earth observation techniques offer unique perspectives to limnology, enabling comprehensive views of multiple aquatic ecosystems simultaneously, regional to global coverage, long-term data collection through time-series analysis, and valuable inputs to predictive models. Moreover, remote sensing facilitates the retrieval of diverse parameters across increasing numbers of smaller lakes, including surface area, elevation, and biogeochemical data.

When applied correctly, remote sensing technologies enable the monitoring of temporal changes across vast numbers of water bodies, helping to identify long-term trends and detect immediate changes in aquatic environments. The growing availability and

potential of remote sensing products for aquatic studies have added a critical spatial dimension to traditional methods. Historical Earth observation data can complement existing long-term monitoring datasets, providing robust support for management and conservation strategies. However, many remote sensing methodologies and products used in applied aquatic studies often receive insufficient attention to their specific limitations and requirements.

A thorough understanding of remote sensing methods for inland waters is essential for their effective application and the accurate interpretation of results. Freshwater ecosystems present significant challenges due to their optical complexity and biogeochemical variability. Common remote sensing products designed for terrestrial or oceanic applications are often unsuitable for inland waters. For instance, atmospheric correction tailored to the unique conditions of inland waters, including adjacency effects, is critical but frequently overlooked. Similarly, misunderstandings about the assumptions and quality of remote sensing products can undermine the reliability of findings in recent limnological research.

This presentation highlights the current and future technical capabilities of remote sensing for inland water quality monitoring, emphasizing the need for stronger connections between the remote sensing, in situ observation, and modeling communities. To address this, harmonized methods and techniques must be developed, optimized, and implemented to monitor the diversity of aquatic habitats while maintaining data integrity amidst evolving methodologies. This raises key considerations for dataset managers: whether to adopt emerging methods or maintain established approaches, and how to ensure data continuity and quality during methodological transitions.

The trend toward collaborative, interdisciplinary research in aquatic sciences - leveraging automated data collection and Big Data (from satellite images and imaging flow cytometry) - further underscores the importance of adaptive strategies for ecosystem monitoring. The growing acceptance of remote sensing technology in limnology, combined with the standardization of satellite-based water quality products and the adoption of new in situ technologies for calibration and validation, presents a unique opportunity for inland water monitoring.

Achieving this vision will require closer collaboration between aquatic scientists, remote sensing experts, and data scientists. Efforts must focus on calibrating and validating new in situ and remote sensing technologies for water quality products using biogeochemical and radiometric data. This will enable users to contextualize results and understand the trade-offs inherent in using these advanced datasets. Greater synergies between these communities are needed to harmonize products, provide training materials and best-practice guides, and re-evaluate earlier findings using improved methodologies. Such efforts will address current limitations and significantly enhance our capacity to monitor and manage rapidly changing inland waters effectively.

Keywords

earth observations, water quality remote sensing, in situ sensing

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KEYNOTE

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.